

Supporting information for „Ex-ante cost estimations for sanitation systems based on mass flows“

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With this document we aim to provide supporting information for Spuhler and Germann (2019). It summarizes the concept for ex-ante cost estimations for sanitation systems based on mass flows as developed in Germann (2019), a Master thesis within the framework of the GRASP project (Generation and Assessment of Sanitation Systems for Strategic Planning) (Spuhler 2018).

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1. Development of a concept to consider the costs of a sanitation system

1.1 General concept

The idea of the developed concept is to use sanitation system (SanSys) specific data, that is available from the system generator and mass flow model developed under the GRASP project, to estimate costs of the generated SanSys'. The mass flows [m³/yr or kg/yr] are used as input into generalized cost functions to first quantify costs per unit of technologies (Techs) contained in the SanSys (see section 1.2), and then to quantify the costs of the entire SanSys in a given urban settlement (see section 1.3). The presented approach can be used to extend the procedure developed by Spuhler et al. (2018) with cost estimations for the generated SanSys.

To quantify the costs, the inflow mass of the different substances (phosphorus, nitrogen, total solids, and water) into a Tech (flow_in_t) is used to parametrize the costs due to the following reasons:

- It is available from the mass flow model for each Tech and hence enables to link the costs of a SanSys to its specific design generated (e.g. it allows the consideration of loops within a SanSys).
- The inflow mass of four substances is available, which enables the selection of the inflow flow that is most relevant for the costs of a specific Tech. This can be either the inflow of one substance or a combination of some substances (e.g. water for the conventional sewer, water plus an estimated total solids (TS) of 20% of water volume as sludge into co-composting).
- Divided by the number of facilities of a Tech (n_t) it results in the inflow mass per facility of the Tech flow_in_{i,t}, is a parameter for the required size of the Tech, and hence a good indicator for the costs of a Tech.

Available cost functions have to be adapted and simplified in a way that they rely mainly on the flow_in_{i,t} as an input parameter. In a generalized way they shall describe the costs of one facility of a Tech c_{Tech,i,t} as a function of flow_in_{i,t}:

$$c_{Tech,i,t} = f_t(\text{flow_in}_{i,t}) \quad \text{Equation 1}$$

Additionally, the costs of a SanSys depend on n_t, which serves as an indicator for the degree of centralization. Hence, to be able to aggregate the costs at the system scale, additionally, n_t has to be defined. n_t can vary widely, from one facility per household to one central facility for a whole town. Certain constraints estimating the minimum and maximum n_t (n_{min,t} and n_{max,t}) have to be defined. Such constraints can, for example, be a minimum or maximum volume of water inflow in order to make one facility of a Tech functional or a minimum or maximum constructible size of a Tech. Also, constraints concerning the validity of a cost function (e.g. the applied anaerobic baffled reactor (ABR) cost function is valid for 10-1000 person equivalent (PE) per unit) can be relevant.

Consequently, the estimated costs for the Techs within a certain SanSys c_{Tech,t} depend not simply on the inflow per facility flow_in_{i,t}, but rather on the total inflow flow_in_t into the Tech and the corresponding number of facilities n_t:

$$c_{Tech,t} = n_t * f_t\left(\frac{\text{flow_in}_t}{n_t}\right), \quad n_t = \{n_{min,t}, n_{max,t}\} \quad \text{Equation 2}$$

Once the $c_{Tech,t}$ are defined for each Tech within a SanSys the range of costs of the whole SanSys c_{Sys} can be estimated by the simple addition of the costs of all Tech from user interface $c_{Tech,U}$ to disposal $c_{Tech,D}$:

$$c_{Sys} = \sum_{t=U}^D c_{Tech,t} \quad \text{Equation 3}$$

Table 1: Overview of the concept for the cost model.

	User Interface (U)	Collection and Storage (S)	Conveyance (C)	On-site and centralized treatment (T)	Use and/or disposal (D)
$c_{Tech,i,t} =$	$f_{U,t}(\text{flow_in}_{i,t})$	$f_{S,t}(\text{flow_in}_{i,t})$	$f_{C,t}(L_i, \text{flow_in}_{i,t})$	$f_{T,t}(\text{flow_in}_{i,t})$	$f_{D,t}(\text{flow_in}_{i,t})$
$c_{Tech,t} =$	$n_t * f_{U,t}(\frac{\text{flow_in}_t}{n_t})$	$n_t * f_{S,t}(\frac{\text{flow_in}_t}{n_t})$	$n_t * f_{C,t}(\frac{\text{flow_in}_t}{n_t})$	$n_t * f_{T,t}(\frac{\text{flow_in}_t}{n_t})$	$n_t * f_{D,t}(\frac{\text{flow_in}_t}{n_t})$
$c_{Sys} =$	$\sum_{t=U}^D c_{Tech,t}$				

1.2 Cost functions

Several assumptions and simplifications have to be applied to adapt available cost functions to (mainly) depend on the flow $\text{in}_{i,t}$. Many available cost functions depend on person equivalent (PE) as an input parameter. These can quite simply be related to the flow $\text{in}_{i,t}$. If, for example, 80 L/d wastewater is the defined PE for a cost function, $\text{flow_in}_{H_2O,t}$ divided by 80 L/d can be used as the required input parameter PE. Others already per definition depend on the inflow (e.g. the Tech composting on the input of dewatered sludge [m^3/yr]).

Techs of the functional group (FG) conveyance (C) are more complex as the main input parameter for cost estimations is the length or distance of transport. Hence, they additionally depend on the estimation of a parameter L. This can either be defined per facility (e.g. average distance to pick up point/per truck) or in total (e.g. estimated sewer length and a corresponding $n_t=1$ sewer system).

$$c_{C,Tech,t} = f_{C,t}(L, \text{flow_in}_{i,t}) \quad \text{Equation 4}$$

In addition to the already introduced Techs, variations of Techs depending on the inflow product (e.g. co-composting with the input product sludge and co-composting with the input product faeces) might be helpful to simplify the cost functions.

Mainly cost functions from the CLARA Simplified Planning Tool (SPT) (Langergraber et al. 2015) were used. For Techs for which no cost functions were available in the CLARA SPT (e.g. user interface Techs), alternative sources for cost functions had to be found. These cost functions had to be compatible with the used Techs. To not double count costs for certain parts or services of a Tech (e.g. include costs for user interface in user interface Tech as well as subsequent storage Tech such as single pit/pit latrines, counting costs for desludging in on-site storage as well as conveyance Tech), details on what costs that are considered in the respective cost functions should be available.

1.3 Minimum/maximum number of facilities

The introduction of a minimum and a maximum number of facilities is based on the assumption that a Tech of FG C only appears once in the SanSys. For the definition of $n_{max,t}$ and $n_{min,t}$ of C Techs as well as Techs that come after a C Tech, some exceptions have to be considered.

Techs coming after a C Tech are following labelled with either an additional index 'AC' (for after conveyance) or 'trans' (for transported).

To be able to estimate the range of costs for a given SanSys, to calculate the minimum ($n_{\min,t}$) and maximum ($n_{\max,t}$) number of facilities per Tech within the SanSys the following constraints can be considered:

- Maximum and minimum inflow or person equivalent for one facility (PE_i , $flow_in_{i,t}$): PE_i is mainly relevant for source Techs. Due to loops, given constraints in PE per facility should be converted into limits of inflow ($flow_in_{i,\min,t}$, $flow_in_{i,\max,t}$) (1.2).
- Maximum and minimum number of parent Techs $p(t)$ per facility $n_{\min,p(t)}$ and $n_{\max,p(t)}$: e.g. the number of facilities n_t per Tech has to be equal or lower than the number of facilities of the preceding Tech $p(t)$ $n_{p(t)}$. For example, $n_{\max,U,UT} \leq n_{\max,S,UDDT}$, in order to not increase the number of facilities from FG U to the following FG S (e.g. the construction of four urine storage tanks (UT) for one urine diverting dry toilet (UDDT) is not allowed). This assumption should not be valid for TAC and DAC Techs.
- Maximum collection area (CA) per facility: with the collection area being defined as the area that can be served by one facility of a Tech or for which costs of transport of input products are considered negligible. It should be especially applied for on-site Techs, meaning Techs before which there is no Tech of FG C included.
- The maximum number of facilities of a Tech has to be at least as high as the minimum number of facilities of that Tech. This can cause that other constraints are not fulfilled (e.g. minimal inflow per facility) and the estimated number of facilities would practically not be operable or only at low capacity rates, still, it fulfils our needs for the estimation of costs ranges.
- Constraints due to limitations in constructions or validity of the used cost functions: e.g. available sizes of septic tanks.
- For Techs that are not per se restricted in size, like the application of faeces, urine or drying beds, the introduction of a 'reference facility' could be defined (e.g. an average field size of two hectares).
- In the case of project areas with low population, a limit of at least one facility of each Tech in the system should be used ($n_{\min,t} \geq 1$).

For the calculation of the n_t , only the constraints of relevance for that specific Tech will be considered, e.g. for the n_t of a user interface Tech, CA should not be seen as a limiting factor. For these Techs, PE_i mostly represents the required n_t sufficiently and CA could lead to a disproportionately high number of facilities, especially in areas with low population density.

Following, some examples for the calculation of $n_{\max,t}$ and $n_{\min,t}$ are shown: Min {} means, that the minimal value of all values within these brackets is chosen, as n_t cannot be higher than every single value defined within these brackets. Max {} means, that the maximal value is chosen respectively.

The number of Techs of user interface (e.g. pour flush) can be limited as follows:

$$n_{\min,U} = \max \left\{ \frac{1}{PE_{i,Shared,t}} \right\} \quad \text{Equation 5}$$

$$n_{\max,U} = PE/PE_{i,U,t} \quad \text{Equation 6}$$

$n_{\min,U,t}, n_{\max,U,t}$ minimum, maximum number of facilities of user interface Tech [unit]

$PE_{i,Shared,t}$ Persons per facility if shared [persons] e.g. for public toilets or toilets shared between households

$PE_{i,U,t}$ (common) persons per facility [persons]

The more constraints are considered, the more complex the calculation becomes. If more than one constraint is available, the one defining the actual $n_{\max,t}$ or $n_{\min,t}$ has to be selected. This is done by choosing the minimum and maximum number available within the respective constraints:

At the example given below, we define a maximal size of collection area covered by one facility of Tech S, hence we need at least one facility of Tech S per collection area within the project area ($n_{\min,S,t} \geq A/CA_{\max,S,t}$). There also is a maximal number of facilities of parent Techs ($n_{\max,p(t)/S,t}$) and a maximal inflow ($flow_in_{i,\max,t}$) allowed per facility of S Tech defined. Therefore $n_{\min,S,t} \geq n_{p(t)}/n_{\max,p(t)/S,t}$ and $n_{\min,S,t} \geq flow_in_{Sys,t}/flow_in_{i,\max,t}$. We choose the maximum of these three values as $n_{\min,S,t}$ has to be higher than each of these values. Still, we have to consider, that $n_{\min,S,t}$ cannot be higher than the minimum number of parent Techs ($n_{\min,p(t)}$). Hence, if $n_{\min,p(t)}$ is lower than the one from the criteria before, $n_{\min,p(t)}$ is the decisive one.

$$n_{\min,S,t} = \min \left\{ \max \left\{ \frac{1}{\frac{A}{CA_{\max,S,t}}}, \frac{n_{p(t)}}{n_{\max,p(t)/S,t}}, \frac{flow_in_t}{flow_in_{i,\max,t}} \right\}, n_{\min,p(t)} \right\} \quad \text{Equation 7}$$

$n_{\min,S,t}$ minimum number of facilities of a Tech of FG storage [unit]

A area of the project [m²]

$CA_{\max,S,t}$ maximum collection area of a Tech [m²]

$n_{p(t)}$ number of facilities of a parent Tech p(t)

$n_{\max,p(t)/S,t}$ maximum number of facilities of a parent Tech p(t) per Tech t of the FG storage [unit]

$flow_in_t$ Input mass into a Tech [kg/yr or m³/yr]

$flow_in_{i,\max,t}$ maximum input mass into one facility of the respective Tech [kg/yr or m³/yr]

Similarly, the maximum number of facilities of the S Tech ($n_{\max,S,t}$) cannot be higher than the maximum number of parent Techs $n_{\max,p(t)}$, therefore $n_{\max,S,t} \leq n_{\max,p(t)}$. Additionally, $n_{\max,S,t}$ is limited by a minimal inflow into one facility $flow_in_{i,\min,t}$ hence $n_{\max,S,t} \leq flow_in_{Sys,t}/flow_in_{i,\min,t}$. Nevertheless, $n_{\max,S,t}$ cannot be lower than $n_{\min,S,t}$, therefore the maximal value between the criteria before and $n_{\min,S,t}$ is selected as $n_{\max,S,t}$.

$$n_{\max,S,t} = \max \left\{ \min \left\{ \frac{\text{flow_in}_t}{\text{flow_in}_{i,\min,t}}, n_{\max,p(t)}, n_{\min,S,t} \right\} \right\} \quad \text{Equation 8}$$

$n_{\max,S,t}$ maximum number of facilities of S Tech [unit]

flow_in_t Input mass into a Tech [kg/yr or m³/yr]

$\text{flow_in}_{i,\min,t}$ minimum input mass into one facility of the respective Tech [kg/yr or m³/yr]

$n_{\max,p(t)}$ maximum number of facilities of parent Tech p(t) [unit]

$n_{\min,S,t}$ minimum number of facilities of a Tech of FG storage [unit]

For C Techs it is difficult to define a number of facilities for a Tech, therefore we look at two illustrative types of C Tech in this thesis exemplary (2.4).

For Techs after a conveyance Tech, CA and $n_{p(t)}$ are not limiting factors, therefore the definition on $n_{\min,AC,t}$ and $n_{\max,AC,t}$ can be simplified to:

$$n_{\min,AC,t} = \max \left\{ \frac{1}{\text{flow_in}_{AC,t} / \text{flow_in}_{i,\max,AC,t}} \right\} \quad \text{Equation 9}$$

$$n_{\max,AC,t} = n_{\min,AC,t} \quad \text{Equation 10}$$

$n_{\min,AC,t}$ minimum number of facilities of a Tech after a C Tech [unit]

$\text{flow_in}_{AC,t}$ Input mass into a Tech [kg/yr or m³/yr]

$\text{flow_in}_{i,\max,AC,t}$ maximum input mass into one facility of the respective Tech [kg/yr or m³/yr]

$n_{\max,AC,t}$ maximum number of facilities of a Tech after a C Tech [unit]

2. Quantification of costs for illustrative examples of sanitation systems in Arba Minch

2.1 Required input

The main input parameter is the flow_in_t , that is calculated within the mass flow model (appendix A. Additional input parameters for cost functions are the sewer length or average distance to a pick-up point, as well as person equivalent (PE) served and PE per household (PE per HH). PE per HH, meaning per user interface facility, have to be estimated.

Estimations for the length of a planned sewer system and the average distance of transport are more complex. As no other data is available, in this study the length of a sewer system is estimated by applying an approach developed by Maurer et al. (2010). Originally, this approach was developed to estimate the length of combined sewers in Switzerland, hence some adoptions were made. Apart from the case-specific geometry data, additionally the runoff coefficient, as well as the specific sewage coefficient per inhabitant were adapted to better represent the case of Arba Minch (appendixB).

The average distance of transport from a household to a treatment size was adopted from Meininger et al. (2010) and estimated to be 15+/-5 km per way.

PE per HH are estimated to be between 5 and 25 if toilet facilities are shared.

Mainly the $flow_{in_{H_2O,t}}$ was used as a link to the mass flow model. For other Techs, the $flow_{in_t}$ of other substances (TS, P or N) might be more relevant, e.g. when dried faeces are the main input product TS are probably the decisive substance. Additional links, e.g. between BOD and TS, could be used to generate relevant input parameters for different Techs.

Besides the required input for the cost functions, for the calculation of n_t the size of the assessed area [m^2] is an additional required input. The area per kebele was estimated from GIS with 1.927 km^2 for Chamo, 1.174 km^2 for Mehal Ketema and 1.095 km^2 for Woze. The collection area is assumed to be 0.02 km^2 for all Techs where this constraint applies.

2.2 Costs functions for a range of sanitation technologies

Cost functions for the following Techs were adopted from Langergraber et al. (2015) and Mastewal (2008) cited in Mindachew (2009) exemplarily: pour flush, single pit, septic tank, ABR, conventional sewer, motorized transport dry, co-composting, horizontal flow constructed wetland. For each of them, a cost function for initial investment costs (IIC), as well as operation & maintenance costs (O&MC), was adapted (Table 2). For technical specifications and details about the validity and applicability see the specific references.

No cost functions for Techs of the FG D were considered, as rather than costs a certain revenue can be generated by them (e.g. the selling of compost or stabilized urine for the application as fertilizer). Still, sometimes the sale of the acquired products might not be beneficial (e.g. due to cultural constraints to apply products deriving from human excreta), while other Techs actually can generate costs (e.g. soak pit). These cases could not be considered within the scope of this thesis.

Table 2: Adapted cost functions for a number of Techs.

Tech	input parameter	variable in cost function	Comment	Conversion flow_in _t to x	IIC per facility [€]	O&MC per facility [€/yr]	reference
Pour flush	PE	-	per facility	-	1102/32.57	435/32.57	Mastewal (2008) cited in Mindachew (2009)
Single pit	flow_in _{H2O, single pit}	Volume of single pit [m ³]	Collection interval: 45 days	$\text{flow_in}_{\text{H}_2\text{O, single pit}}/365 \cdot 45/\text{h}$	$(-4.8639 \cdot x^2 + 241.94 \cdot x + 1287.2)$	$(-4.8639 \cdot x^2 + 241.94 \cdot x + 1287.2)$	Cesspit
Septic tank	flow_in _{H2O, septic tank}	PE	with 80L/PE/d influent	$\text{flow_in}_{\text{H}_2\text{O, septic tank}}/80 \cdot 1000/365/\text{h}$	if $(x > 20)$ $(x^0.564 \cdot 329.5)$ else $(x^0.468 \cdot 665.4)$	$x^0.415 \cdot 9.4$	Septic tank
ABR	flow_in _{H2O, ABR}	PE	with 80L/PE/d	$\text{flow_in}_{\text{H}_2\text{O, ABR}}/80 \cdot 1000/365/\text{h}$	if $(x < 400)$ $x^0.4844 \cdot 821.9480$ else $x^2 \cdot (-0.012) + x \cdot 35.488 + 3009.788$	$x^0.4579 \cdot 7.9850$	ABR
Co-composting	flow_in _{H2O, co-composting}	dewatered sludge [m ³]	TS=20%, valid for co-composting with dewatered sludge, no costs for bulking material considered (Arba Minch Town Water Supply and Sewerage Enterprises 2013)	$\text{flow_in}_{\text{H}_2\text{O, co-composting}} \cdot 1.25/365/\text{h}$	$(x^5/3)^0.799 \cdot 18799.290$	$(x^5/3)^0.766 \cdot 817.041$	Composting
horizontal flow constructed wetland	flow_in _{H2O, HSSFCW}	required area [m ²]	estimated area required per PE=5m ² , no pump, with 80L/PE/d influent	$\text{flow_in}_{\text{H}_2\text{O, HSSFCW}}/80 \cdot 1000/365/\text{h}$	if $x \leq 135$ $x^*61.672 + 1866.586$ else $x^*57.775 + 5571.575$	if $x \leq 135$ $x^*1.047 + 30.178$ else $x^*1.026 + 33.586$	HFCW
conventional sewer	length of sewer, flow_in _{H2O, conventional sewer} , PE, PE per HH	length, PE, specific inflow [L/PE/d], PE per HH and others	see Langergraber et al. (2015) for details	$\text{flow_in}_{\text{H}_2\text{O, conventional sewer, PE}}$	costs.manholes+costs.sewer = cost.per.manhole*number.of.manholes+costs.per.meter*(sewer.length-diameter.manholes)+f1(sewer.depth)*sewer.length/average.distance.manholes+f2(sewer.depth)*f3(specific.inflow, DN, PE.per.HH, PE.served ...)-diameter.manholes)	0.02 * IIC	Sanitary sewer
motorized transport dry	average distance to pick-up points, η_{dry} (motorized.transport.dry), flow_in _{H2O, motorized.transport.dry}	average distance to pick-up point, number of pick-up points, volume per interval and pick-up point	see Langergraber et al. (2015) for details	$\text{flow_in}_{\text{H}_2\text{O, motorized.transport.dry}}/365/\eta_{\text{dry}}$ (motorized.transport.dry)	unit price of vacuum truck=52195.27 (from unit costs according to Langergraber et al. (2015))	annual gasoline costs + maintenance costs + labour costs = gasoline.price*gasoline.consumption*total.distance +0.1*number.of.vehicle*unit.price.vacuum.truck+number.of.vehicle*hours.per.day*working.days.per.year*(unit.craftsman+unit.unskilled.labour)	Collection of (faecal) sludge

2.3 Transferability of the cost functions

The cost functions are based on unit costs and an exchange rate (ETB to Euro) of 1/32.57 (finanzen.net 2019), and therefore case specific. Within the CLARA SPT cost functions for a number of countries (Uganda, Burkina Faso, Kenya, South Africa and Morocco) based on bills of quantities (BOQs) and unit costs of different commodities and services were established. Hence for these countries, the cost functions could quite easily be adapted, by using the established BOQs.

For other countries, establishing case-specific BOQs and unit costs would be quite time-consuming and simply using the exchange rate as a conversion factor to estimate local costs ($C_{Sys,local}$) would be very imprecise. Alternatively, an approach using the cost per square metre for constructing a standard single storey residential building (C_{RB} and $C_{RB,local}$ [costs/m²]) as conversion factor as suggested by Loetscher (1999) could be used. The relation can be simplified as follows:

$$C_{Sys,local} = C_{Sys} * \frac{C_{RB}}{C_{RB,local}} \quad \text{Equation 11}$$

$C_{Sys,local}$	costs of a SanSys for a specific location [local currency, local currency/yr]
C_{Sys}	costs of a SanSys as calculated with the established cost functions [€, €/yr]
C_{RB}	costs per square metre for constructing a standard single storey residential building of reference case (Arba Minch)
$C_{RB,local}$	local costs per square metre for constructing a standard single storey residential building in the case area

Compared to adapting case specific BOQs, this approach is a lot less time-consuming. Another advantage of using the C_{RB} is, that it is quite easily available to the user and can generally be obtained from local builders. As it is determined by several parameters such as the cost of labour, of energy, and of commodities, and can be seen as an indicator for a construction event in general (Loetscher 1999). As the information will be used in the structuring phase of the SDM process, the level of accuracy would be good enough for the application. However, the application of this approach could not be done within the scope of this thesis.

2.4 Examples of calculation of the number of facilities per Tech

Following some illustrative examples for the calculation of n_t are shown: one for a user interface Tech, one for an on-site Tech, two C Techs (conventional sewer and motorized transport dry) and one for a Tech after a C Tech, are shown:

Pour flush (user interface):

As values for $PE_{i,U,t}$ and $PE_{i,Shared,t}$ for the considered user interface Techs we define 5 and 25 persons as number of users respectively. Looking at the example of Chamo with 10,374 PE, therefore $n_{max,U}$ and $n_{min,U}$ can be calculated as:

$$n_{min,U} = \max \left\{ \frac{1}{25} \right\} = 415 \text{ units} \quad \text{Equation 12}$$

$$n_{\max,U} = \frac{10374}{5} = 2075 \text{ units} \quad \text{Equation 13}$$

This number is the same for all SanSys' in Chamo.

Single pit (on-site):

The calculation of $n_{\text{Single.pit}}$ is illustrated at the example of SanSys 66356 in Chamo. The cost function used for the Tech single pit is valid for a pit volume between 1.8-18 m³ and an emptying interval of 45 days (Langergraber et al. 2015). The volume available per single pit per year ($\text{vol_per_year}_{\text{Single.pit}}$) can, therefore, be defined as:

$$\text{vol_per_year}_{\text{Single.pit}} = \text{vol}_{\text{Single.pit}} * 365/45 \quad \text{vol}_{\text{Single.pit}}[\text{m}^3] = \{1.8, 18\} \quad \text{Equation 14}$$

The collection area ($CA_{\max,\text{Single.pit}}$) is estimated to be 0.02 km² and the area of Chamo (A) 1.927 km². $\text{flow_in}_{\text{Single.pit,H}_2\text{O}}$ is calculated by the mass flow model to be 31428 m³/yr. $n_{\min,p(\text{Single.pit})}$ is calculated using Equation 5 to be 414.96.

Therefore, as defined by Equation 7, $n_{\min,\text{Single.pit}}$ is:

$$\begin{aligned} n_{\min,\text{Single.pit}} &= \min \left\{ \max \left\{ \frac{1}{CA_{\max,\text{Single.pit}}} \right\}, \frac{\text{flow_in}_{\text{Single.pit,H}_2\text{O}}}{n_{\min,p(\text{Single.pit})}} \right\} = \min \left\{ \max \left\{ \frac{1}{0.02}, \frac{31428 / (18 * \frac{365}{45})}{414.96} \right\} \right\} \\ &= \min \left\{ \max \left\{ \frac{1}{96.35}, \frac{1}{215.26} \right\}, \frac{1}{414.96} \right\} = 215.26 \end{aligned}$$

$n_{\max,p(\text{Single.pit})}$ is calculated using Equation 5 to be 2074.80 and therefore $n_{\max,\text{Single.pit}}$ is estimated by Equation 8 as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} n_{\max,\text{Single.pit}} &= \max \left\{ \min \left\{ \frac{\text{flow_in}_{\text{Single.pit,H}_2\text{O}}}{n_{\max,p(\text{Single.pit})}}, \frac{\text{flow_in}_{\text{Single.pit,H}_2\text{O}}}{n_{\min,\text{Single.pit}}} \right\} \right\} = \max \left\{ \min \left\{ \frac{31428 / (1.8 * \frac{365}{45})}{2074.80}, \frac{31428 / (1.8 * \frac{365}{45})}{215.26} \right\} \right\} \\ &= \max \left\{ \min \left\{ \frac{2152.6}{2074.80}, \frac{2152.6}{215.26} \right\} \right\} = 2074.80 \end{aligned}$$

Conventional sewer (C Tech):

No constraints for the length or inflow into one facility of conventional sewer (one sewer system) is specified, therefore we define:

$$n_{\min,\text{Conventional.Sewer}} = n_{\max,\text{Conventional.Sewer}} = 1 \text{ sewer system} \quad \text{Equation 15}$$

$n_{\min,\text{Conventional.Sewer}}$ minimum number of facilities of conventional sewer [unit]

$n_{\max,\text{Conventional.Sewer}}$ maximum number of facilities of conventional sewer [unit]

Motorized transport dry (C Tech):

For the Tech 'motorized transport dry' n_t equals the number of trucks required and is defined as follows:

$$n_{\min, \text{motorized.trans.dry}} = \max \left\{ \frac{1}{n_{\min, p(t)} / \text{loc. per. vehicle}} \right\} \quad \text{Equation 16}$$

$$n_{\max, \text{motorized.trans.dry}} = \max \left\{ \frac{1}{n_{\max, p(t)} / \text{loc. per. vehicle}} \right\} \quad \text{Equation 17}$$

$n_{\min, \text{motorized.trans.dry}}$ minimum number of facilities of motorized transport dry [unit]

$n_{\max, \text{motorized.trans.dry}}$ maximum number of facilities of motorized transport dry [unit]

loc.per.vehicle locations served by one vehicle [unit]

The location served by one vehicle is calculated by the locations that can be served by one vehicle per day times the working days per year. The locations per day are defined by different factors such as the number of trips per location, the time spent at each location, the estimated average distance to a pick-up point, average speed, collection interval, vehicle load and the volume collected per location per interval. For details see Langergraber et al. (2015).

ABR transport (after conveyance):

The calculation of n_{ABR} is illustrated at the example of SanSys 66431 in Mehal Ketema. According to Langergraber et al. (2015), the applied cost function is valid from 10-1000 PE with 80L/PE/d blackwater inflow. The volume available per ABR per year ($\text{vol_per_year}_{\text{ABR}}$) can, therefore, be defined as:

$$\text{flow_in}_{i, \text{AC, ABR}} = \text{vol}_{\text{ABR}} * 365 \quad \text{vol}_{\text{ABR}} [\text{m}^3] = \{1000 * 80 / 1000\} \quad \text{Equation 18}$$

$\text{flow_in}_{\text{AC, ABR, H}_2\text{O}}$ is calculated by the mass flow model to be 17485 m³/yr. Hence $n_{\min, \text{AC, ABR}}$ is calculated using Equation 9 to be:

$$n_{\min, \text{AC, ABR}} = \max \left\{ \frac{1}{\frac{\text{flow}_{\text{in}_{\text{AC, ABR, H}_2\text{O}}}}{\text{flow}_{\text{in}_{i, \max, \text{AC, ABR}}}}} \right\} = \max \left\{ \frac{1}{17485 / (1000 * \frac{80}{1000})} \right\} = 1$$

$n_{\max, \text{AC, ABR}}$ is defined by Equation 10 with: $n_{\max, \text{AC, ABR}} = n_{\min, \text{AC, ABR}} = 1$

$$n_{\max, \text{AC, ABR}} = n_{\min, \text{AC, ABR}} = 1$$

Similarly, $n_{\max, t}$ and $n_{\min, t}$ were calculated for all other Techs using the defined constraints (appendixC).

2.5 Illustrative examples for quantification of costs in Arba Minch

To illustrate the developed concept the costs for a number of SanSys' were calculated. To select the SanSys' of which costs should be calculated, the following criteria were considered:

- For the Techs in the SanSys' applicable cost functions had to be available.
- Each SanSys should be amongst the selected ones in at least one kebele.
- At least one SanSys of each kebele, as well as one to show the example of conventional sewer and motorized transport dry, should be considered, in order to illustrate all aspects of the concept (e.g. Techs after conveyance).
- As far as the above-mentioned criteria allow, SanSys' with different conceptual and structural properties should be present.

The calculation was written in RStudio (RStudio Team 2016). In the beginning, some preparatory data is defined, including a selection of the kebele and SanSys' for which the costs shall be calculated. For the available SanSys', the costs can then be calculated automatically.

The code subsequent code is divided into different sections. First kebele and SanSys specific data and inflows into the Techs as calculated by the mass flow model are specified. Then, some matrices required for the calculation are defined. In the next section, constraints for the number of facilities are determined for each Tech to subsequently be able to calculate the maximum as well as the minimal number of facilities. In the next step, cost functions for the different Techs are defined. Finally, the costs for every Tech are calculated and then aggregated to costs for the whole SanSys.

It can be downloaded from the following link:

https://gitlab.com/VerenaG/costs_of_sansys_based_on_mass_flows.git

3. Results of illustrative examples of cost quantification for Arba Minch

The costs for the following SanSys' were estimated: 66194 for all three kebeles, 66356 for Chamo, 66431 for Chamo and Mehal Ketema, 66617 for Mehal Ketema (Table 3). SanSys 66194 is an example of ST.1 (Dry onsite storage with sludge production without effluent transport) and has a quite low recovery potential. SanSys 66356 is similar but has a septic tank instead of a single pit. It is an example of ST.15 (Onsite blackwater with sludge without effluent transport) and has quite high recovery ratio for all substances. SanSys 66431 was only selected for Chamo, as comparative example also the costs for Mehal Ketema were calculated. It is an example of ST.19 (Offsite blackwater treatment) and includes a conventional sewer, therefore it is estimated not be appropriate for Woze. SanSys 66617 is another example of ST.15 but includes motorized transport for sludge transport. It has quite high recovery ratio for all substances.

Figure 1: SanSys' for which costs have been calculated.

The cost ranges of these SanSys' (c_{Sys}) are based on the input data described in appendix 0 and B and are summarized in Table 3. A summary of the breakdown of the cost ranges for each Tech ($c_{\text{Tech},t}$) can be found in appendix D.

Table 3: Cost estimations for some SanSys’.

Kebele	Inhab.	SanSys	C _{sys}							
			IIC [€]		O&MC [€/yr]		IIC [€/PE]		O&MC [€/PE/yr]	
			min	max	min	max	min	max	min	max
	PE									
Chamo	10374	66194	1,542,992	4,296,787	45,442	107,461	148.74	414.19	4.38	10.36
Mehal Ketema	6634		982,682	2,743,688	28,847	68,506	148.13	413.58	4.35	10.33
Woze	15250		2,101,156	6,149,292	58,117	149,285	137.78	403.23	3.81	9.79
Chamo	10374	66356	484,072	540,232	20,778	42,946	46.66	52.08	2.00	4.14
Chamo	10374	66431	367,007	547,881	14,242	38,905	35.38	52.81	1.37	3.75
Mehal Ketema	6634		271,404	405,736	9,958	26,102	40.91	61.16	1.50	3.93
Mehal Ketema	6634		66617	282,142	331,654	15,082	30,073	42.53	49.99	2.38

The results in Table 3 show estimations for minimal and maximal IIC and O&MC based on the developed concept.

Amongst the SanSys’ for which costs have been calculated SanSys 66194 seems to have the highest costs, which is caused by the high costs for the Techs Single pit and Co-composting (appendix D). The reason for that is the estimated high number of facilities required for these Techs (appendix C).

Looking at n_t of SanSys 66194, we can see, that the $n_{\text{Cocomposting}}$ is lowest for Woze although Woze has the highest population of all assessed kebele. This is because in the calculation of $n_{\text{Cocomposting}}$ A/CA is the decisive factor and Woze is estimated to have the lowest area (2.3).

Taking the example of SanSys 66617 in Mehal Ketema, we can observe that O&MC of motorized transport dry is slightly higher for the minimal number of facilities per Tech than for the maximum number (8,210 to 7,526; appendix D). The reason for that is a higher sludge volume that has to be collected per location per interval if fewer pick-up-points are installed (17.1 m³ compared to 14.6 m³). Due to the given volume of the truck (5 m³) the load factor per trip is lower for the lower number of locations, leading to a higher number of trips required per location (4 instead of 3) which cannot be compensated by the lower number of locations served (59 instead of 69).

For more details, interpretation, conclusions and outlook see the full version of the thesis (Germann 2019)

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Appendix

A. Inflows from mass flow model (flow_{int})

Inflows [kg/yr P, N, TS or m³/yr for H₂O] calculated using the mass flow model.

Kebele	SanSys	Inflow	Pour-flush	Single pit		Co-composting	
Chamo	66194	P [kg/yr]	4,711	4,711		3,015	
		N [kg/yr]	29,732	29,732		5,352	
		H ₂ O [m ³ /yr]	31,428	31,428		4,714	
		TS [kg/yr]	324,883	324,883		194,930	
Mehal Ketema	66194	P [kg/yr]	3,013	3,013		1,928	
		N [kg/yr]	19,013	19,013		3,422	
		H ₂ O [m ³ /yr]	20,098	20,098		3,015	
		TS [kg/yr]	207,757	207,757		124,654	
Woze	66194	P [kg/yr]	6,926	6,926		4,432	
		N [kg/yr]	43,706	43,706		7,867	
		H ₂ O [m ³ /yr]	46,200	46,200		6,930	
		TS [kg/yr]	477,584	477,584		286,551	
			Pour-flush	Septic tank		Co-composting	
Chamo	66356	P [kg/yr]	4,711	4,711		1,413	
		N [kg/yr]	29,732	29,732		5,946	
		H ₂ O [m ³ /yr]	31,428	31,428		1,571	
		TS [kg/yr]	324,883	324,883		107,211	
			Pour-flush	Conventional Sewer	ABR trans	HSSFCW	Co-composting trans
Chamo	66431	P [kg/yr]	4,711	4,711	4,240	2,841	2,564
		N [kg/yr]	29,732	29,732	23,785	16,888	11,289
		H ₂ O [m ³ /yr]	31,428	31,428	27,342	25,975	1,614
		TS [kg/yr]	324,883	324,883	292,394	122,806	208,887
Mehal Ketema	66431	P [kg/yr]	3,013	3,013	2,711	1,817	1,640
		N [kg/yr]	19,013	19,013	15,210	10,799	7,219
		H ₂ O [m ³ /yr]	20,098	20,098	17,485	16,611	1,032
		TS [kg/yr]	207,757	207,757	186,981	78,532	133,579
			Pour-flush	ABR	Motorized transport dry	Co-composting trans	
Mehal Ketema	66617	P [kg/yr]	3,013	3,013	994	974	
		N [kg/yr]	19,013	19,013	5,514	5,293	
		H ₂ O [m ³ /yr]	20,098	20,098	804	780	
		TS [kg/yr]	207,757	207,757	120,499	118,089	

B. Adaptions of UWIM for estimation of sewer length

Input data for UWIM (Maurer 2009) to estimate the length of the sewer system.

	unit	Chamo		Mehal Ketema		Woze	
area	m ²	1.927*1000 ²		1.174*1000 ²		1.095*1000 ²	
shape factor of the catchment area (f1), length:width	-	2		3		2	
shape factor of the housing plots (f2)	-	1.2		1.2		1.2	
number of inhabitants €	persons	10374		6634		15250	
PE per HH	persons	5	25	5	25	5	25
number of buildings	-	2074.8	414.96	1326.8	265.36	3050	610
specific sewage coefficient per inhabitants (Q.E.spez)	m ³ *(cap*s) ⁻¹	8.3/(1000*24*3600) (from 8.3 L water/(cap*d) for pour flush)					
runoff coefficient (psi)	-	0					
Estimated length of sewer	m	21165	10247	17319	8703	25361	12124

C. Constraints and the corresponding number of facilities per technology

For details see 1.3, 2.5 and Langergraber et al. (2015).

Formula	Tech	Constraints	flow_int [m³/yr, m²]	SanSys / kebele						
				66194		66356		66431		66617
				Chamo	Mehal Ketema	Woze	Chamo	Chamo	Mehal Ketema	Mehal Ketema
min	Pour flush	5-25 PE per facility	min	415	265	610	415	415	265	265
max			2075	1327	3050	2075	2075	1327	1327	
min	Single pit	1.8-18 m³ per facility, emptying interval: 45 days	min	215	138	316	-	-	-	-
max			2075	1327	3050	-	-	-	-	
min	Septic tank	5-2000 PE with 80L/PE/d per facility, emptying interval: twice a year (if PE<20 once a year)	min	-	-	-	96	-	-	-
max			-	-	-	96	-	-	-	
min	ABR	10-1000 PE with 80L/PE/d	min	-	-	-	-	-	-	59
max			-	-	-	-	-	-	-	69
min	Co-composting	1-500 m³ total compostable waste volume per day	min	96	59	55	96	-	-	-
max			96	59	55	96	-	-	-	
min	Conventional sewer	number of facilities = one sewer	min	-	-	-	-	1	1	-
max			-	-	-	-	1	1	-	
min	Motorized transport dry	Vehicle load (truck) = 5 m³, average distance to from household to treatment sit 15+/-5 km	min	-	-	-	-	-	-	1
max			-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
min	ABR trans	10-1000 PE with 80L/PE/d	min	-	-	-	-	1	1	-
max			-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
min	Co-composting trans	1-500 m³ total compostable waste volume per day	min	-	-	-	-	1	1	1
max			-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
min	HSSFCW trans	4-2000 PE with 80L/PE/d, 5m² area estimated to be required per PE	min	-	-	-	-	1	1	-
max			-	-	-	-	-	-	-	

D. Detailed cost estimations

Kebele	SanSys	Costs	Pour flush		Single pit		Co-composting		HSSFCW		Co-composting trans		min	max		
			min	max	min	max	min	max	min	max	min	max				
Chamo	Tech	C _{tech} [€]	-												Sum	
			14,040	70,200	875,295	3,572,929	653,657	653,657								1542992.3
		O&MC [€/yr]	5,542	27,711	10,270	50,120	29,630	29,630							45442.4	107,461
			8,978	44,892	559,737	2,284,829	413,967	413,967							982,682	2,743,688
		IIC [€]	3,544	17,721	6,568	32,051	18,735	18,735							28,847	68,506
			20,639	103,196	1,286,704	5,252,283	793,813	793,813							2,101,156	6,149,292
O&MC [€/yr]	8,147	40,735	15,097	73,677	34,872	34,872							58,117	149,285		
	Tech		Pour flush		Septic tank		Co-composting		-		-		Sum			
Chamo	66356	IIC [€]	14,040	70,200	198,352	198,352	271,679	271,679						484,072	540,232	
			5,542	27,711	2,466	2,466	12,770	12,770							20,778	42,946
	Tech		Pour flush		Conventional Sewer		ABR trans		HSSFCW		Co-composting trans		Sum			
Chamo	66431	IIC [€]	14,040	70,200	117,049	241,762	25,718	25,718	99,366	99,366	110,834	110,834		367,007	547,881	
			5,542	27,711	2,341	4,835	183	183	1,699	1,699	4,477	4,477		14,242	38,905	
Mehal Ketema	66617	IIC [€]	8,978	44,892	99,406	197,824	19,957	19,957	65,552	65,552	77,510	77,510		271,404	405,736	
			3,544	17,721	1,988	3,956	149	149	1,099	1,099	3,177	3,177		9,958	26,102	
	Tech		Pour flush		ABR		Motorized transport dry		Co-composting trans		-		Sum			
Mehal Ketema	66617	IIC [€]	8,978	44,892	158,989	172,587	52,195	52,195	61,980	61,980				282,142	331,654	
			3,544	17,721	1,447	1,577	7,526	8,210	2,564	2,564				15,082	30,073	